

Application form: Open Science Infrastructure (2024) - full proposal

Section 1: Applicants

Name of the main applicant Dr John Swinbank
 Affiliation – institution NWO-I ASTRON
 Affiliation – department n.a.
 Position Science Data Centre Programme Manager
 End date of contract Permanent Position
 Guarantee needed & added yes/no/n.a. n.a.
 E-mail address
 ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9445-1846>

Name of the co-applicant Dr Jason Maassen
 Affiliation – institution Netherlands eScience Center
 Affiliation – department n.a.
 Position Technology Lead
 End date of contract Permanent Position
 Guarantee added yes/no/n.a. n.a.
 E-mail address
 ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8172-4865>

Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title LoFAIR: FAIR Data & Open Software for LOFAR
 Project duration (in months) 24

English public summary

LOFAR is the world's largest telescope operating at low radio frequencies, addressing an extraordinary range of science cases, from black holes and pulsars to extrasolar planets. However, LOFAR's impact is limited because both the data it produces and the software needed to analyse it are hard to find and awkward to access. LoFAIR will address this by making the LOFAR data archive fully compliant with the FAIR principles and introducing a centralized directory for analysis tools based on the established Research Software Directory. For a relatively small investment, this dramatically increases the accessibility of LOFAR to the widest scientific community.

Word count EN-SUM (max 100): 100

Dutch public summary

LOFAR is 's werelds grootste telescoop voor lage radiofrequenties, gericht op een buitengewoon scala aan wetenschappelijke onderwerpen, van zwarte gaten en pulsars tot exoplaneten. De impact van LOFAR wordt echter beperkt doordat zowel de geproduceerde data als de benodigde analysesoftware moeilijk vindbaar en toegankelijk zijn. LoFAIR pakt dit aan door het LOFAR-data-archief volledig te laten voldoen aan de FAIR-principes en door een gecentraliseerde directory voor analysetools te introduceren, gebaseerd op de bestaande Research Software

Directory. Met een relatief kleine investering wordt hiermee de toegankelijkheid van LOFAR voor de bredere wetenschappelijke gemeenschap aanzienlijk vergroot.

Word count NL-SUM (max 100): 93

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

LOFAR [1], the world's largest low-frequency radio telescope, provides a combination of field of view, sensitivity, and angular resolution that enables a wide range of high-impact science. It produces extremely large (terabytes to petabytes) datasets that are preserved in the Long Term Archive (LTA), the world's largest astronomical data archive, with ~50PB stored.

LOFAR's goal [2] is to fully adhere to the principles of Open Science, Open Access, and FAIR data. However, its existing systems are inadequate: aging technology and inhomogeneous software pose a number of challenges. LoFAIR will overcome these challenges through two initiatives:

- Upgrading the LTA to fully support the FAIR principles.
- Providing a centralized location for describing and distributing the software needed to use the data.

A focused investment here will enable a major research infrastructure to fully embrace Open Science, rendering the user community more productive and making it accessible to a wider range of non-specialists.

Word count SEC31 (max. 150): 150

3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

LOFAR's impact has been limited by two challenges:

- The LTA is built on a data model and technology stack that pre-date the modern conversation around Open Science and FAIR data. While data products are available, they are hard to discover, awkward to access, and described by limited metadata.
- Much of the software used to process and analyze LOFAR data has been produced by the distributed and heterogeneous academic research community. Although open source, the software is hard to find, hard to use, and frequently abandoned or obsoleted by staffing turnover, while the contribution of developers and engineers is easily marginalized.

Addressing these will:

- Make the existing expert community more productive, by reducing the overhead involved in working with LOFAR data.
- Make LOFAR data accessible to a wider audience within the astronomical research community without deep LOFAR expertise.
- Provide a forum in which software engineers can showcase and receive credit for their contributions.
- Reduce the burden on the staff supporting the LTA.

Given the specialist nature of the archive and huge data volumes involved, there is no other infrastructure which can fill this role. However, engaging with the Research Software Directory team at NLeSC enables us to build on existing systems.

Word count SEC32 (max. 200): 200

3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

- This project explicitly aims to increase the openness of the LOFAR telescope by improving access to both data and software in line with Open Science principles.
- LOFAR ERIC, as stated in its Data Policy [2], is committed to open and transparent science data. All LOFAR datasets will be made freely available after any applicable proprietary period.
- The FAIR LOFAR Data Archive will make data available following FAIR principles, by building on community standards for data description and access as expressed through the IVOA.
- The LOFAR Software Directory will build on the existing open-source [Research Software Directory](#) codebase

Open Science Infrastructure 2024 full proposal - Small

to increase the level of access to open-source analysis software in the astronomical community. We will provide support for authors contributing to the LOFAR Software Directory to follow the FAIR4RS guidelines.

- All software developed during this project will be open source, released following the ASTRON Open Source Policy [3] or NLeSC equivalent.

Word count SEC33 (max. 200): 149

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

This project proposes to make a number of incremental improvements to well established systems. In particular:

- The [LOFAR LTA](#) is an extant system, which is both currently operational (serving science users) and undergoing incremental upgrades in conjunction with the LOFAR2.0 system upgrade.
- The LTA data model is mature, and was designed with attention to appropriate tracking of metadata and provenance information. The model is now old — the LTA was developed around two decades ago — and so we propose to upgrade and modernize it, not fully rethink it.
- Astronomy has historically been a leader in data modelling and standardization. The [International Virtual Observatory Alliance](#) (IVOA) defines [standards](#) for representing a wide variety of astronomical data products, including metadata and [provenance](#). Work is ongoing to incorporate radio astronomy data into these standards with ASTRON playing a prominent role.
- The [Research Software Directory](#) is a major project led and maintained by the [Netherlands eScience Centre](#), which already tracks information about more than 500 software products written by over 1100 contributors. It has been transformational to the way the global scientific community publishes software.
- ASTRON already maintains and publishes a variety of tools which are critical to working with LOFAR data, and has close connections with the authors of other tools across the research community.

In short, while the aims of this project are ambitious and have high impact, they are based on a rich and well-supported ecosystem: this project really is building on a legacy of previous innovation and existing best practice.

The project is structured as two work packages — FAIR Data Archive and LOFAR Software Directory — each of which contains a series of related tasks as described below.

Work Package 1: FAIR Data Archive

Task 1.1: Standardization of Radio Astronomy Data Models (2 PMs, start M1, end M12)

- Represent the Netherlands in the IVOA Radio Astronomy Interest Group.
- Guide IVOA data models to be relevant to the LOFAR archive.
- Undertaken by ASTRON Software Engineer 1 & System Architect.

Task 1.2: Development of FAIR Data Representation in the LTA (6.5 PMs, start M2, end M13)

- Modify the existing LTA schema to support all of the FAIR principles.
- A test system and demonstrate successful operation.
- Undertaken by ASTRON Software Engineer 1 & System Architect.

Task 1.3: Roll Out New LTA Structure & Migrate Existing Data (6.2 PMs, start M14, end M19)

- Deploy an LTA catalogue based on the new schema on production infrastructure.
- Migrate data from the existing LTA.
- Decommission the old LTA, replacing it with the new system
- Undertaken by ASTRON Software Engineer 1 & System Architect.

Task 1.4: LTA Interface Enhancements (3 PMs, start M20, end M24)

Open Science Infrastructure 2024 full proposal - Small

- Upgrade the LTA user interface to enable end users to make full use of the FAIR data model.
- Undertaken by ASTRON Software Engineer 1 & System Architect.

Work Package 2: LOFAR Software Directory

Task 2.1: Establish Requirements for LOFAR Software Directory (1.6 PMs, start M9, end M12)

- The ASTRON and NLeSC teams will agree on detailed requirements and design concepts for the Software Directory.
- Undertaken by Instrument Scientist & RSD team.

Task 2.2: Initial Test Version of LOFAR Software Directory for ASTRON Use (3.5 PMs, start M13, end M17)

- The NLeSC team will deliver an initial version of the LOFAR Software Directory.
- The ASTRON team will seed this system with a collection of ASTRON-developed software.
- The ASTRON team will explore and test this system, feeding results back to NLeSC for further refinement.
- Undertaken by Instrument Scientist, ASTRON Software Engineer 2 & RSD team.

Task 2.3: Refined LOFAR Software Directory for Public Use (3.0 PMs, start M18, finish M22)

- An upgraded system is delivered, based on feedback received from Task 2.2
- The system is announced and made available to the science community.
- The system is seeded with software drawn from ASTRON and across the community.
- Undertaken by Instrument Scientist, ASTRON Software Engineer 2 & RSD team.

Task 2.4: Training & Support to the LOFAR Community (1 PMs, start M20, finish M24)

- An ongoing programme of education and training is established to help members of the science community benefit from the Software Directory.
- This work will continue after the project duration, as described in §5.1.
- Undertaken by Instrument Scientist.

Word count SEC41 (max. 750): 733

4.2 Team composition

Name, surname	Affiliation	Expertise	Role/Contributions
	NWO-I/ASTRON	Radio astronomy, software development, project management	PI
	NWO-I/ASTRON	System architecture, data management	System Architect
	NWO-I/ASTRON	Python software development, astronomical data archives	ASTRON Software Engineer #1
	NWO-I/ASTRON	Python software development, distributed systems, system management	ASTRON Software Engineer #2
	NWO-I/ASTORN	Astronomy data, scientific support	Instrument Scientist
	NLeSC	Frontend development & requirements engineering	RSD Developer

NLeSC

Parallel and distributed programming, efficient computing

RSD Product Owner

Word count SEC42 (max. 350): 99

4.3 Risk management

Risk

LOFAR2.0 delayed, causing late availability of ASTRON staff & infrastructure.

Likelihood and impact

Likelihood: medium
Impact: medium

Risk mitigation strategy

- WP1 includes schedule contingency; staff could be assigned at a higher fractional FTE for a shorter period.
- LoFAIR tasks can be interleaved with other LOFAR2.0 upgrade activities
- IVOA standards could guide development and bring interoperability benefits, but it will be possible to proceed without them.
- Future LTA upgrades could retrofit IVOA support.

IVOA does not deliver appropriate standards in a timely fashion.

Likelihood: high
Impact: low

The established LOFAR science community has existing software distribution channels, and may not engage with the Directory.

Likelihood: medium
Impact: medium

- IVOA standard process.
- Training and education programme.
- ASTRON staff will help onboard existing software.
- Adoption will increase with time as the new members join the community.

Word count SEC43 (max. 150): 145

4.4 Budget

Position	HOT scale	Institution	Total FTE	Years active	Amount
Project Manager	HOT 2.1 - 14	NWO-I/ASTRON	0.10	2	€ 14,769.50
System Architect	HOT 2.1 - 13	NWO-I/ASTRON	0.25	2	€ 33,197.50
ASTRON Software Engineer #1	HOT 2.1 - 11	NWO-I/ASTRON	0.80	2	€ 80,216.00
ASTRON Software Engineer #2	HOT 2.1 - 10	NWO-I/ASTRON	0.30	1	€ 26,422.50
Instrument Scientist	HOT 2.1 - 9	NWO-I/ASTRON	0.30	1	€ 23,983.50
RSD Developer	HOT 2.2 - 13	NLESC	0.30	1	€ 47,560.50
RSD Product Owner	HOT 2.2 - 14	NLESC	0.05	1	€ 8,672.00

Material/IT Type	Description	Cost calculation	Total (€)
national symposium/conference/workshop organised by the project itself;	LTA development workshops	€6300 per workshop, including travel, accommodation, catering	€ 12,600.00
(international) travel and accommodation expenses incl. conference visit	Regular project team travel between ASTRON and NLeSC	€50 round trip, two visits per month for 24 months	€ 2,400.00

Total Personnel requested: € 234,821.50

Total Material/IT requested: € 15,000.00

Total budget requested: € 249,821.50

4.5 Budget justification

The majority of the budget is allocated to staff costs at ASTRON and NLeSC. These cover a range of positions, and provide the technical and the scientific expertise that are required to enable the project vision. Their roles and how their time will be allocated is described above.

In addition, we expect to organize two LTA development workshops — one per year — during the conference. These will include members of the project team and the wider LTA community (users and developers) and will focus on rolling out new functionality focused on FAIR data access to the LTA. The funds here are intended to provide catering for the workshop and accommodation and travel support for participants who do not have their own resources.

Finally, we will support regular travel for project members between ASTRON and NLeSC.

Word count SEC 45 (max. 200): 134

4.6 Impact plan

The project is focused around its impact on the astronomy community. On successful completion:

- Existing expert LOFAR users will find data and tooling easier to access, increasing their productivity and the impact of the instrument.
- Members of the wider astronomical community who are not specialist radio astronomers or experts in LOFAR will find it easier to discover, access, and work with data that can help address their science cases.
- Enthusiastic members of the general public will also find it easier to access and understand the data that is being generated by a major taxpayer-funded infrastructure.

In addition, by contributing to the development of data models within the context of the IVOA (Task 2.1), the project will have an impact on the way that astronomical data is published across a wide range of infrastructures and archives, as well as on improving interoperability of data across the astronomical landscape.

Further, the LOFAR Software Directory will provide a platform for the software developers and engineers who are critical to making data-intensive infrastructures like LOFAR successful to showcase their work and receive appropriate acknowledgement. This will help secure the position of research software engineering in astronomy as a valid career track.

Word count SEC46 (max. 200): 198

Section 5: Sustainability and software management

Section 5.1: Sustainability plan

Both the (upgraded by this project) LOFAR Long Term Archive and the (delivered by this project) LOFAR Software Directory will need to be sustained for the long term. This includes development effort (for maintenance and potential upgrades), operational effort, and effort to provide support to members of the scientific community engaging with these services. In addition, infrastructure to host the LTA and the Software Directory will need to be provided both during the period of performance of the project and after it has been completed.

These sustainability needs are addressed by embedding the project within the established LOFAR ecosystems. On completion, both the upgraded LTA and the Software Directory will be incorporated into the portfolio of data services operated under the management of ASTRON's Science Data Centre Operations and offered to the [LOFAR ERIC](#) (European Research Infrastructure Consortium).

The LTA is already a core part of the LOFAR Data Services. The upgrades delivered by this project are not expected to increase operational or support costs after the work has been completed, so FAIR support will be supported indefinitely — until the complete archive is closed, or until technology and operational practices require a different approach.

The Software Directory is a new addition to the portfolio. It is recognized by LOFAR and ASTRON as a valuable service, and it is expected that operation will continue indefinitely. However, it will be regularly reviewed in terms of value delivered to the community and the resources available for its operation.

Word count SEC51 (max 300): 245

Section 5.2: Software management plan

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

Two substantial software development efforts will be undertaken as part of this project: an upgrade to the LOFAR LTA codebase to enable FAIR support, and production of a customized version of the Research Software Directory system appropriate for use by the LOFAR community.

Both of these codebases are used to provide services to the scientific community in the form of web applications. That is, end users are not (generally) expected to download and work with the application or its source code directly, but rather to interact with it through a website.

The web applications will ultimately be run and supported by the ASTRON Science Data Centre Operations group and its partners.

2. How will you manage versioning of your software?

Both the LTA and the RSD codebases have established versioning policies that we will adhere to.

3. How will you make your software publicly available? What licence will your software have?

All software developed by ASTRON is covered by the [ASTRON Open Source Policy](#) and made available through the ASTRON GitLab system at <https://git.astron.nl/> (unless that conflicts with third party licenses or confidentiality agreements). Software released under the Open Source Policy is normally governed by the [Apache License, version 2.0](#).

Some minor changes to the Astro-Wise codebase from which parts of the LTA catalogue are derived may be necessary. Copyright to Astro-Wise is not held by ASTRON and its source code is not currently publicly available. However, the source for any change submitted to Astro-Wise will also be published through ASTRON GitLab.

Open Science Infrastructure 2024 full proposal - Small

The Research Software Directory codebase is available from GitHub (<https://github.com/research-software-directory>) and is also covered by an Apache 2.0 license. Any code developed by NLeSC in the course of this project will follow the same model.

4. How will users of your software be able to cite your software?

The ASTRON Open Source Policy requires that all ASTRON-developed software should be accompanied by a digital object identifier and/or a scientific paper to facilitate citation. In addition, for this project, we propose to embed a CITATION.cff file in the relevant repositories.

The Research Software Directory repository already contains citation metadata pointing to a DOI on Zenodo. This model will be adopted for any updates undertaken in the course of this project.

5. How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.

Both the LOFAR LTA and the Research Software Directory already provide extensive documentation:

- [LTA User Manual](#)
- [LTA Howto](#)
- [RSD Documentation](#)

This documentation will be updated to incorporate the new results delivered in the course of this project. If necessary, a separate documentation system devoted to the specifically LOFAR Software Directory may be provided as a variation on the existing RSD documentation.

6. How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?

We will provide information in software repositories in the conventional forms (e.g. CONTRIBUTING.md, CODE_OF_CONDUCT.md).

7. How will your software be tested?

Both ASTRON and NLeSC make extensive use of automated testing / continuous integration using GitLab CI/CD and/or GitHub Actions.

8. How will you check that it respects the licences of libraries and dependencies it uses?

The OSPREY team is experienced in software licensing, and will audit new dependencies as they are added to the codebase and ensure that their licenses are appropriately recorded and acknowledged. Furthermore, we will investigate tooling such as [Tortellini](#), provided by the Netherlands eScience Center, to automate this process.

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

Source code will be made available through Git repositories (linked above), while compiled / deployable applications are packaged into Docker containers.

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised?

Science users accessing the web applications will receive support through the SDC Helpdesk, a service which is already operated by the ASTRON Science Data Centre Operations group.

The software itself will be maintained and self-supported by the devops team within ASTRON.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

The software will become part of the digital services provided for LOFAR, managed by ASTRON and supported by various partners in LOFAR ERIC. As such, ASTRON development teams and/or their partners will assume responsibility for the software until it is formally retired.

Section 6: References

- [1] [van Haarlem, M.P. et al.](#), *LOFAR: The LOw-Frequency ARray*, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, Volume 556, id.A2 (2013).
- [2] [Bonati, I. and Vermeulen, R.](#), *Science Data Policy of LOFAR ERIC*, v1.0 (2023).
- [3] [Grange, Y. et al.](#), *ASTRON Open Source Policy*, v2.0, 10.5281/zenodo.7307162 (2020).

Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.